

TABLE I—EXPERIMENTAL CONDITIONS FOR ELECTROCHEMICAL PREPARATION OF COMPLEXES

Compd.	Initial voltage V	Initial current A	Time of electrolysis h	Amount of metal dissolved g	Yield		E _f mol F ⁻¹
					g	%	
K ₂ [TiF ₆]	5	0.50	2.0	0.400	1.5	75	0.22
K ₂ [CrF ₆]	2	0.04	3.0	0.085	0.3	65	0.36
K[MnF ₆]	2	0.05	2.0	0.100	0.2	73	0.49
K ₂ [FeF ₆]	8	0.45	2.0	0.600	1.9	62	0.32
Cs ₂ [FeF ₆]	8	0.45	2.0	0.600	4.3	71	0.32
K[CoF ₆]	5	0.30	3.0	0.780	1.3	63	0.39
Cs[CoF ₆]	5	0.30	3.0	0.780	2.7	82	0.39
K[NiF ₆]	4	0.05	2.5	0.180	0.3	63	0.65
Cs[NiF ₆]	4	0.05	2.5	0.180	0.5	66	0.65

from aqueous solution. But the present method uses an aqueous medium at room temperature for all the compounds.

Experimental

The metals were in the form of rods or foils and were mostly 99.8% pure. Chromium and manganese were previously deposited on a platinum foil by electrolysis of their salt solutions and were subsequently used as anodes.

For the preparation of the complexes, electrolysis was carried out using a platinum foil (1 × 1 × 0.1 cm) as the cathode and the appropriate metals connected with platinum wire electrical leads as the anode. Aqueous HF (20%; 10 ml) was used for electrolysis. After electrolysis, the solutions were filtered to free from any disintegrated metal particles. The potassium and the caesium salts were precipitated by adding concentrated solutions of KF or CsF in HF (20%). The complexes were dried in a desiccator over KOH. The details of the experimental conditions are given in Table 1.

Fluorine was analysed by titration with Th(NO₃)₄ after steam distillation of fluorosilicic acid⁶. Potassium and caesium were determined by AAS method. Other metals were determined by standard titrimetric or gravimetric methods.

Results and Discussion

Table 1 shows that fluorides of some 3d-metals can be easily prepared from aqueous HF at room temperature. The applied voltage was small (2–8 V) and the yield was very good (60–85% based on the amount of metal dissolved). The main reactions taking place at the electrodes are

These were evident from the observed electrochemical efficiency (number of moles of metal dissolved per Faraday of electricity passed). A slight deviation of the electrochemical efficiency (E_f) (Table 1) from the theoretical value of 1/n was ascribed to disintegration of metal anode into fine particles, evolution of oxygen at the anode and slight fluctuation of current during electrolysis.

The compounds were characterised by chemical analysis, and the comparison of their magnetic moments^{4,7} and band positions in the electronic spectra^{4,8} with those given in the literature.

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An Attempt to Separate Bentonite and Alumina from their Binary Mixtures

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LONG-chain quaternary ammonium cations can replace the exchangeable cations present on certain clays, viz. montmorillonite, and the resulting clays have the important property of dispersion in a variety of organic solvents. Several workers have studied the change in the organophilic characteristics and other physical properties of organo-clay complexes¹⁻³ and

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the conditions for separating the component clay minerals from binary mixtures by selective coagulation and electrophoresis². According to them a favourable condition for separation by selective coagulation is obtained when one component of the mixture has zero zeta potential and is coagulated, while the other component under the same condition has a high zeta potential and forms a stable suspension. In the present discussion, attempts have been made to separate the component minerals from the mixture of bentonite and alumina by selective coagulation and differences in organophilic behaviour of organo-clay complexes in the light of earlier observations³ of binary mixtures of clay minerals.

Experimental

The clay organic complexes were prepared by reacting aqueous suspensions of clay (1%) with aqueous solutions of cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB) and cetylpyridinium chloride (CPC). The experimental procedures for separation involve coagulation by 0.001 *N* CTAB or CPC of aqueous suspension of clay mixture and solvent extraction of organic complexes of clay mixture using nitrobenzene and water. In the solvent extraction method, the sample was first wetted with water and then nitrobenzene was added. The purity of the separated fractions was judged by total intake of water and toluene, C estimation and X-ray analysis.

Results and Discussion

The results of separation of bentonite and alumina from their mixtures based on coagulation by CTAB are shown in Table 1. Those of solvent extraction using nitrobenzene and water are shown in Table 2.

TABLE 1—STUDIES OF SEPARATED CLAY FRACTIONS FROM BENTONITE-ALUMINA MIXTURE (1 : 1) BY COAGULATION WITH CTAB

Sample	%C in sample	Intake of toluene (ml g ⁻¹ sample)	Intake of water (ml g ⁻¹ sample)
Bentonite fraction separated from mixture	10.05	5.46	1.00
Alumina fraction separated from mixture	1.14	2.22	1.15
CTA-bentonite	11.20	5.41	0.58
CTA-alumina	1.35	1.62	1.22

For conducting the separation process by coagulation, preliminary investigations were carried out on base exchange capacity, sedimentation, flocculation and deflocculation. The concentrations were so adjusted that one of the components remained flocculated and the other deflocculated. Deflocculation of alumina owing to charge reversal precedes that of bentonite.

TABLE 2—STUDIES OF SEPARATED CLAY FRACTIONS FROM ORGANIC DERIVATIVE OF BENTONITE-ALUMINA MIXTURE BY SOLVENT EXTRACTION METHOD

Sample	%C in sample	Intake of toluene (ml g ⁻¹ sample)	Intake of water (ml g ⁻¹ sample)
CTA-derivative of bentonite and alumina mixture (1 : 1)	4.92	3.52	1.10
CTA-bentonite fraction separated from mixture	9.74	5.45	0.68
CTA-alumina fraction separated from mixture	1.42	1.65	1.20

Presumably, the presence of a large number of organic groups on the surface of bentonite makes it highly organophilic, whereas alumina with smaller number of organic groups is still hydrophilic in character. The highly organophilic bentonite complex goes to the nitrobenzene layer, whereas alumina complex has been retained in the water layer.

The X-ray diffractogram for the mixture of CTA-bentonite and CTA-alumina gave strong peaks at 17.0, 3.46, 2.54, 2.37 and 2.08 Å. Strong reflection at 17.0 Å is due to the presence of bentonite complex and reflections at 3.46, 2.54, 2.37 and 2.08 Å are due to the alumina complex. The absence of strong reflections at 3.46, 2.54, 2.37 and 2.08 Å in CTA-bentonite fraction separated from the mixture indicates that CTA-bentonite has been separated from the mixture. The X-ray diffractogram for the CTA-alumina fraction has no reflection at 17.0 Å. The X-ray analysis suggests that the two components of the mixture have been separated to a great extent.

It is to be noted that owing to strong adsorbability of the organic molecules on clays, their complete removal from the separated clay fractions could not be effected. However, it was found that a solution of 0.1*N* HCl in acetone is quite effective.

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